

RECENT FINDINGS ON THE EARLY IRON AGE IN THE BHANDARA DISTRICT AND WAINGANGA BASIN, VIDARBHA

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Introduction

The Early Iron Age/Megalithic culture of Vidarbha is well documented and studied by many scholars for over the past almost one and half century (Carnac 1879, Pearse 1869, Carrey 1881, Hunter 1933, Deo 1970 a&b, 1973a, b & c, 1982 a&b, 1985; Deo and Jamkhedkar 1982, Deglurkar and Lad 1992, IAR 1985-8, 1987-88, 1989-92; Mohanty 1993, 1999a&b, 2002, 2003 a&b, 2004, 2005 a&b; Mohanty and Walimbe 1993, 1996; Mohanty and Joshi 1996, Ismail 2006, Thakuria 2010 and Vaidya 2014). These studies have contributed immense information about the burial typology, burial furniture, burial goods, iron and bronze technology, bead manufacturing and more recently, settlement pattern of the Early Iron Age. The Early Iron Age in Vidarbha is mostly known from the number of megalithic burials present in the region; many of them being excavated over the past one and half century. Along with these, many habitation sites are also known from the region (Vaidya 2014). The Early Iron Age/Megalithic people were producers of fine quality of iron, excellent horse-riders, builders of finest of the burial monuments and also practicing a well established agro-pastoralism. However, when one browses through the literature available (both

published and unpublished) it can be easily noticed that the data is mostly confined to Nagpur and Wardha districts. In comparison the area to the east of Wainganga is relatively less studied.

The earlier excavations by Deo and Joshi (1970) of the classic site of Pauni in Bhandara district, on the banks of the Wainganga, only revealed evidence of the Early Historic period. Excavations by ASI (Nath 1998) at this site have extended the occupation into the Early Iron age. Adam, another fortified site in Kuhi taluka of Nagpur District and very close to the Wainganga also yielded evidence of the Early Iron Age (IAR 1988-89: 50-62; 1990-91: 45-50; 1991-92: 63-68). These findings indicated that evidence for the Early Iron Age in the Wainganga region and Bhandara district might be expected. Consequently, sites like Bhawar (IAR 1992-93: 55-62) and Pachkheri (Nath 2002) also yielded evidence of the Early Iron Age. Pachkheri has also given evidence of menhirs along with stone circles.

Recently, Sontakke (Sontakke 2014a) intensively studied the part of the Upper Wainganga Valley in Gondia District. His investigations have brought to light a couple of habitation sites and around ten burial sites of the Early Iron Age period. A new type

of megalithic monument (Sontakke 2014b) was identified. The burial-cum-habitation site of Malli was also excavated by Sonatakke. The excavations at Malli have revealed new features in the Megalithic culture of Vidabara. The inner architecture of megaliths is uncommon and different than of the Nagpur region and the burial repertoire is also almost negligible (Sontakke 2014a, Sontakke and Bhoyar 2014). Recent study in the Nagpur region by Vaidya (Vaidya 2014) has also changed the outlook towards the Vidarbha megalithic culture. It has brought forth certain important inferences like the presence of agrarian settlements on river banks, the division of society in a semi-complex society and the also the role of raw material sources like coal and iron ore in the location of settlements.

This work, suggests that perennial rivers, mineral resources and trade/exchange were important factors the Early Iron Age culture. This gave further impetus to further explore the region as well as extending the area to be explored. Hence the authors conducted a short but intensive survey in March 2015 in the region of Wainganga and further on the banks of the Chulbandh River in Bhandara district. The results were rewarding and will be discussed in this paper.

Recent Exploration

The authors conducted survey in the vicinity of the Wainganga basin and also in Bhandara district. It yielded five more sites of the Early Iron Age. They are described below.

1. Deori-Kalan ($21^{\circ}2.5'$ N , $79^{\circ}2.5'$ E; Toposheet No. 55 O/8) (Fig. 1): The site is located in Kuhu taluka of Nagpur. It is

Fig. 1 : The Mound at Deori Kalan

about 2-3 km away from the Bhivkund caves (dated to 2nd-3rd cent. AD). The site is located at the end of the village on the right hand side of Mandhal road. The site is located in the farmland of Dnyaneshwar Khedekar. It is close to a small nalla which empties in the Wagh river and is not very far from Wainganga banks. The site is about 7-8 acres and circular in shape. The deposit is not more than 3 m. The ceramics found are Micaceous Red Ware, Black and Red Ware and also Matt Red Ware. Ceramics of the Early Historic period are also found.

2. Ambhora-Mendha ($21^{\circ}1.5'$ N, $79^{\circ}36.5'$ E; Toposheet No. 55 O/12) (Fig. 2): The site is located in Kuhu taluka, on the right bank of the river Wainganga and before one crosses the backwaters of the river to reach Ambhora. It is hence named as Ambhora-Mendha. The mound appears insignificant from the road although it has almost 2 m of archaeological deposit, most probably due to the backwaters encroaching upon

Fig. 2 : The Mound at Ambhora-Mendha

it. It is under cultivation and is circular in shape. The surface has a scatter of Early Medieval and Early Historic ceramics. However, from some dug out places and the eroding slope, pottery like Black and Red Ware and Matt Red Ware were recovered. This affirms its affinity to the Early Iron Age.

3. Katangdhara-Sasara ($20^{\circ}58.303' N$, $79^{\circ}56.982' E$; Toposheet No. 55O/16) (Fig. 3): As one proceeds from Lakhani taluka headquarters towards the east on NH-6, there is a right turn towards Miregaon. From Miregaon to Sasara village, one needs to cross the river Chulbandh. As soon as one crosses the

Fig. 3 : Mound at Katangadhara-Sasara from the side of Chulbandha River

river, there is a habitation mound. The road to Sasara cuts through the mound and it has left open sections. There is another mound exactly adjacent to the site and is under cultivation and falls in the jurisdiction of Sasara whereas the earlier mound is in the Katangdhara village area. Pottery found contains Micaceous Red Ware, Black and Red Ware, Black Burnished Ware, Matt Red Ware and Black on Red Ware. Together both the mounds measure around 12-13 acres and the deposit is around 3 m. However, soil quarrying is destroying the site. The site is located in Sakoli taluka.

4. Sasara ($20^{\circ}58.263' N$, $79^{\circ}57.14' E$; Toposheet No. 55P/13) (Fig. 4): The site is just behind the village Sasara itself. It is only half a km from the site of Katangdhara-Sasara. It has a deposit of around 5 m. The site is almost filled with iron slag, vitrified in nature and lumps of it coming out when dug in the ground, besides iron ore also being present there. The site was probably an iron smelting site. The site has yielded pottery like Red Slipped Ware of Early

Fig. 4 : A Part of the mound at Sasara with the lake

Historic period. The presence of red ware having a sharp undercut on the exterior and a beaded rim, red ware with reflex angle and obliquely undercut on the exterior is indicative of an earlier period. Such ceramics are present in the Mauryan and pre-Mauryan period at Pauni (Nath 1998). Thus there is a possibility of the presence of the Early Iron Age at the site. It is further testified by the presence of a menhir and some large stones resembling cap-stones of cists in the field on the northern slope of the site (Fig. 5). The site is located on the bank of a lake, which is on the north and the west of it. The menhir is located just on the bank of this lake.

Fig. 5 : The menhir and loose capstones at Sasara

5. Korambhi (21°7.495'N, 79°37.344'E; Toposheet No. 55O/12) (Fig.6): The site is located on the right bank of Wainganga in Bhandara taluka of Bhandara district. The site is near the water works of the ordnance factory and also under present day village. It has a deposit of around 5- 6 m. The area of the site is around

Fig. 6 : Mound at Korambhi from the bank of Wainganga

15-17 acres spread on two mounds. The site has a thick deposit of the Early Historic period. However, there is the presence of the Early Iron Age, attested by the typical ceramics like Micaceous Red Ware, Black Burnished Ware, Black and Red Ware and also red ware of matt variety and painted red ware. In the village the habitation is disturbed by the present day villagers and the water works.

Discussion

The finding of new sites has opened a new arena in study of the Early Iron Age. It can be seen as follows:

- a) The observation of Vaidya (2014) that there are and have to be many more sites with Early Iron Age habitation and also that the habitation and burials form one single cultural entity is supported. Hence, it can be said that there are settlements present in areas rich in resource like alluvium, pasture and iron ore.

Fig. 7 : Map of Vidarbha showing the important excavated sites and newly explored sites

b) Malli excavations (Sontakke 2014a) as discussed earlier have brought out some new aspects of the Early Iron Age such as the presence of a different burial architecture, negligible burial goods and also the importance of internal burial architecture more than the interments. Recent explorations have yielded only solitary evidence of menhir from Sasara. Menhirs are not very common in the Nagpur region, except at Nagbhir and Umred. But even the last mentioned two places are near the Wainganga River. Even at Malli and surroundings menhirs are noticed (Sontakke 2014a). Thus it can be said that this burial typology was confined probably to the Wainganga proper and not in the Nagpur region and

further west. Also it seems that the burials differed in ideology from the Nagpur region, since at Malli not many burial goods were recovered as in the Nagpur region burials (Sontakke 2014a). Again this suggests the presence of a different burial type like menhir and cist in this region. Sasara and its surroundings therefore make up a promising place for further probing and investigations.

c) The presence of sites in the Chulbandh region suggests the tendency to appropriate forest wealth as well as the exploitation of iron ore present in the region. Even at Malli, the excavators have reported iron slag from the excavation (Sontakke 2014a). Thus it can

be said that this region was very important from the point of view of iron smelting in the Early Iron Age.

- d) The differential approach towards the burials in this region creates a possibility of a different group of people engaged in iron smelting and supplying the Nagpur region, since only Naikund and Shirkanda have given evidence of iron smelting there which cannot be sufficient for the entire region.
- e) In fact, the region of Nagpur seems to be engaged in active exchange with the region further east of it. Although the material culture of these two regions is similar, burial customs differ, leading the possibility that the communities had different identities.
- f) Newly discovered sites are situated near to the bank of perennial rivers and have close association to lakes near to the sites. It is also observed that the sites are situated close proximity to the forest, availability of suitable agricultural land, favorable rainfall and availability of raw material in form of iron ore etc. must have played significant role in emergence and development of Early Iron Age sites in this part of the Vidarbha.

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